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**CULTURE HISTORY OF AFRICA AND INTERNATIONAL DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS:
A STUDY OF NIGERIA AND SOUTH AFRICA**

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ABSTRACT: Nigeria's relations with South Africa were of double standard during the apartheid era. The post-independence Nigeria and the apartheid regime in Pretoria relations were sour and confrontational, while it was friendly between Nigeria and the liberation movements in South Africa, especially with the African National Congress (ANC). It was more so because Nigeria adopted Africa as the centerpiece of its foreign policy, and committed itself to the total liberation of the African continent from colonialism and racism. Nigeria staged untiring opposition to colonialism on the African continent, and the racism that existed in South Africa before 1994. The beginning of a new era started in the final days of apartheid in South Africa when President de Klerk visited Nigeria in April 1992 to discuss bilateral issues, mostly trade relations. This paper looks into Nigeria and South Africa artistic evolution some 70,000 years ago and salient trade networks which began around 2500 B.C.E. However examining diplomatic fluidity since re-establishing formal relations in 1994, to understand causes of those misunderstanding and its effect on both countries' relations, while suggesting better ways to foster diplomacy. The study argues that Nigeria plays big brother roles in Africa from 1960 but is now unable to continue with such big brother projects. South Africa on the other hand quickly recognized economic opportunities in Africa and seek to establish neo-imperial post in the continent. However, the study suggests that the two African giants can have a smooth relations but Nigeria needs to step up its development in order to create parity with South Africa to help them form alliance of strength for Africa. It also notes that South Africa is the real giant of Africa, but Nigeria covers her internal weaknesses while engaging in diplomacy, especially with South Africa.

Keywords: Diplomatic relations, bilateral relations, General Sani Abacha, Nelson Mandela, democratizing, African renaissance, foreign policy in Africa, big brother Nigeria and neo-imperialist south Africa, African giants, yellow fever.

1 Introduction

This research aims at exploring and explaining major diplomatic failures between the two most powerful nations in Africa, since 1994 with the possibility of understanding causes and impact on diplomacy of these Africa giant nations. The two countries have the two largest economies in Africa, South Africa taking the lead because of her more capitalized economy with advantage in infrastructure, science and technology, while Nigeria is the second largest economy in Africa owing to her population and the blessings this most populous black nation in the world enjoys in oil as well as human resources

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(see Marwa, 2010). The state of Nigeria has suffered many years of squandering at the hands of her erstwhile military leaders and politicians (Idowu, 2008). This has been a major setback in the body politics of Nigeria.

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This essay base on comparative politics uses content-analysis based on literature, electronic, and print media to explore the diplomatic breakdowns of these two most influential countries in sub-Saharan Africa. Adopting a qualitative method of research, the essay describes and analyses the two major diplomatic crises between Nigeria and South Africa. This study uses Nigeria's withdrawal from the 1996 African Cup of Nations hosted by South Africa, and the most recent deportations of travelers between these two countries owing to yellow fever vaccination card scandal to argue that; failure of these two countries to form a workable alliance is a setback to their diplomacy and as such have impacted productivity most negatively.

One of the reasons for using content-analysis based on secondary data is because the necessary data for the examining the diplomatic crises of Nigeria and South Africa is already available in literature, electronic, and print media.

Another reason is that it would be impossible to interview the individuals involved in those crises and even if they would be met for interviews their views might not be relied upon since they might be biased in their versions of the story. These make content-analysis based on secondary data the most suitable methodology for this study.

2.0 Africa History from 300 BCE and Nigeria-South Africa Diplomacy Since 1994

Humankind's origins and the beginnings of cultural expression may be traced to Africa. Recent discoveries in the southern tip of Africa provide remarkable evidence of the earliest stirrings of human creativity. Ocher plaques with engraved designs, made some 70,000 years ago, represent some of humankind's earliest attempts at visual expression. Although much remains to be learned about Africa's ancient civilizations through further archaeological research, such discoveries suggest tantalizing possibilities for rich insights into human as well as artistic evolution.

Rock paintings depicting domesticated animals provide artistic evidence of the existence of agricultural communities that developed in both the Sahara region and southern Africa by around 7000 B.C.E. As the Sahara began to dry up, sometime before 3000 B.C.E., these farming communities moved away. In the north, this led to the emergence of art-producing civilizations based along the Nile, the world's longest river. Egypt, one of the world's earliest nation-states, was unified as a kingdom by 3100 B.C.E. Further south along the Nile, one of the earliest of the Nubian kingdoms was centered at Kerma in present-day Sudan and dominated trade networks linking central Africa to Egypt for almost one thousand years beginning around 2500 B.C.E.

The earliest evidence of civilizations in Nigeria dates back to the Iwo-Eleru rock shelter located near Akure in Ondo State. Inside this cave is a skeleton dated c. 9000 B.C.E in the Late Stone Age. Archeological evidence from the Iron Age is more abundant, particularly from the Nok. This civilization was comprised of agriculturalists skilled in iron smelting who lived between 500 BCE and 200 B.C.E. Miners in 1943 unearthed numerous clay pots and terracotta sculptures used by the Nok. Similarly, the Taruga flourished around 300 BCE. Several notable developments in the 11th century dramatically shaped the cultural landscape and political organization of Nigeria's early peoples.

Amina was born in the middle of the sixteenth century CE to King Nikatau, the 22nd ruler of Zazzau, and Queen Bakwa Turunku (r. 1536–c. 1566). She had a younger sister named Zaria for whom the modern city of Zaria (Kaduna State) was renamed by the British in the early twentieth century. According to oral legends collected by anthropologist David E. Jones, Amina grew up in her grandfather's court and was favored by him. He carried her around court and instructed her carefully in political and military matters.

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At age sixteen, Amina was named Magajiya (heir apparent), and was given forty female slaves (kuyanga). From an early age, Amina had a number of suitors attempt to marry her. Attempts to gain her hand included “a daily offer of ten slaves” from Makama and “fifty male slaves and fifty female slaves as well as fifty bags of white and blue cloth” from the Sarkin Kano.

After the death of her parents in or around 1566, Amina's brother became king of Zazzau. At this point, Amina had distinguished herself as a “leading warrior in her brother's cavalry” and gained notoriety for her military skills. She is still celebrated today in traditional Hausa praise songs as “Amina daughter of Nikatau, a woman as capable as a man that was able to lead men to war.”

Between 200 000 and 100 000 years ago, modern humans began to evolve throughout Africa – including South Africa. They became the San, who later met up with south-bound Khoi pastoralists from the north and became known collectively as the KhoiSan.

The San were South Africa's first people.....

The KhoiSan drifted down into the Western Cape at about the same time (300AD) that early Iron Age groups crossed the Limpopo – whose descendants, about 1 000 years later, formed the African kingdom of Mapungubwe and began to trade with India, Arabia and China.

In 1652, Jan van Riebeeck and his 90-strong party arrived from The Netherlands and set up a ship-refuelling station at Cape Town – an important stop both geographically and politically, as it was on the only early trade route from Europe and the Americas to India, the ‘Spice Islands’ of the East Indies, and the East. Over the next 200 years, various waves of other European and Indian settlers also arrived. Subsequently, the Dutch, British and to an extent, the French, fought for control of the Cape, with the British finally triumphant in 1806. Dutch Boers prepared to trek into the hinterland to escape British rule. This was also the start of the Mfecane (‘the scattering, the crushing’) of Africans that began in Zululand, crossed the Drakensberg and swept through the present Free State province. Spurred on by the Zulu warrior king Shaka’s growing militarism, it became a confusing maelstrom of movement and massacre. Adding the land-hungry Voortrekkers and the newly arrived 1820 British Settlers into this mix brought further conflict.

The late 1800s saw the discovery of South Africa’s immense gold and diamond wealth, and later, the great platinum finds. The 20th century saw the end of the South African War (also known as the Second Anglo-Boer War), which was fought from 1899 to 1902; the establishment of the Union of South Africa in 1910; the involvement in World War I and World War II on the side of the Allies; a narrow victory for the mostly Afrikaner National Party in 1948; and, in the years to come, the formulation of apartheid. Apartheid was a nearly 50-year period of institutionalised racism and the suppression of non-whites, during which the African National Congress was banned and its leaders, including Nelson Mandela, banished to prison on Robben Island. The unbanning of the ANC, the release of Mandela and his fellow prisoners, and the 1994 democratic elections heralded the birth of the new South Africa.

Social groups in Nigeria did not live in isolation. Instead, they formed segmented political polities, kingdoms, and empires, particularly around 1000 CE. Even nomadic peoples, such as the Fulani, moved in clearly organized political structures. These early peoples established diplomatic and economic networks that stretched across long distances. For example, royalty from Borno in the northeastern corner of Nigeria sent 100 camels, 100 horses, and 100 articles of clothing to a king in Borgu situated in eastern

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Nigeria. The most studied kingdoms and empires that developed around the 11th century were the Hausa kingdoms and the Oyo Empire. According to oral tradition, the Hausa kingdoms developed from a marriage between Prince Bayajidda of Baghdad and a princess from Daura around the 10th century. One version of the story says their son, Bawo, and his sons established the first several Hausa kingdoms, which include Daura, Kano, and Katsina, to name a few.

The establishment of early political units, such as the Hausa Kingdoms, however, was not without negotiation or dispute. Land, for instance, was traded, purchased, and stolen. The founder of the town of Ilesha in southwestern Nigeria, according to oral tradition, purchased the site from a chief at Oyo for four slaves (male and female), two cows, one horse, 200 bundles of cowries, and 100 kola nuts. A kingdom at Kanem, however, was invaded and dismantled in 1389 by the nomadic Bulala people who desired the area for their own temporary settlement. The history of Nigeria between 1000 and 1800 included the rise and fall of kingdoms as well as the expansion of long distance and international trade.

A corpus of sophisticated terracotta sculptures found over a broad geographic area in present-day Nigeria provides the earliest evidence of a settled community with ironworking technology south of the Sahara.

The strategic location of the Inland Niger Delta, lying in a fertile region between the Bani and Niger rivers, contributed to its emergence as an economic and cultural force in the area. Excavations there at the site of Jenne-jeno ("Old Jenne," also known as Djenne-jeno) suggest the presence of an urban center populated as early as 2,000 years ago. The city continued to thrive for many centuries, becoming an important crossroads of a trans-Saharan trading network. Terracotta figures and fragments unearthed in the region reveal the rich sculptural heritage of a sophisticated urban culture (see the Seated Figure, above).

By the ninth century, trade across the Sahara had intensified, contributing to the rise of large state societies with diverse cultural traditions along trade routes in the western Sudan as well as introducing Islam into the region. Initially traversed by camel caravans beginning around the fifth century, established trans-Saharan trade routes ensured the lucrative exchange of gold mined in southern West Africa and salt from the Sahara, as well as other goods. Ghana, one of the earliest known kingdoms in this region, grew powerful by the eighth century through its monopoly over gold mines until its eventual demise in the twelfth century.

Between the 1870s and 1900, Africa faced European imperialist aggression, diplomatic pressures, military invasions, and eventual conquest and colonization. At the same time, African societies put up various forms of resistance against the attempt to colonize their countries and impose foreign domination. By the early twentieth century, however, much of Africa, except Ethiopia and Liberia, had been colonized by European powers.

The European imperialist push into Africa was motivated by three main factors, economic, political, and social. It developed in the nineteenth century following the collapse of the profitability of the slave trade, its abolition and suppression, as well as the expansion of the European capitalist Industrial Revolution. The imperatives of capitalist industrialization—including the demand for assured sources of raw materials, the search for guaranteed markets and profitable investment outlets spurred the European scramble and the partition and eventual conquest of Africa. Thus the primary motivation for European intrusion was economic¹ (Ehiedu E.G Iweriebor).

The expectations around the world that Nigeria would play a pivotal role in the reviving of Africa after its independent on 1 October 1960 had diminished to a great extent at the time South Africa re-entered the comity of nations as a democracy in the 1994. The only memorable thing left was remembrance of Nigeria's role in the liberation of Africa from colonialism, and the special support she

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gave to the abolition of apartheid in South Africa (see Aremu, 2013). The diminishing influence of Nigeria could be blamed on her economy, which failed largely because of the successive military regimes in the country.

However, the new democratic regime in Pretoria, the popular government of national unity (GNU) led by the antiapartheid icon, President Nelson Mandela, quickly established bilateral relations with Nigeria in 1994, though the latter was under the military leadership led by late General Sani Abacha. The move was in recognition of Nigeria's role in the liberation of apartheid South Africa. Though the formal relationship was established between Nigeria and South Africa, Banjo (2010) remarked that the Mandela-Abacha relationship did not measure up to African expectations because it was characterized by mistrust and conflict between the two administrations (also see Aremu, 2013). One of the major issues was the demand by President Mandela that Nigeria should democratize in line with the Harare Declaration in 1991 by the Commonwealth Heads of State and Government (see Ndlovu, 2010).

Pretoria's assumption of moral authority to advise on democracy and the advancement of human rights was based on what South Africa had adopted as her pillars of foreign policy after 1994, but was misinterpreted by Nigeria's military junta as an attempt by Pretoria to set up competition between the two countries which Nigeria claimed she was not interested in (Banjo, 2010). Nigeria's side of the argument was in itself a distortion of the facts. For example, military involvement in politics was already out of fashion in the world. The relationship between the two countries was tense because of Abacha's desire to hang onto power, and gross abuse of human rights in Nigeria (Banjo, 2010).

Nigeria had witnessed successive military juntas led by Major-General Mohammadu Buhari which cut short about five year old democracy led by President Shehu Shagari. On 27 August 1985 there was another military takeover in Nigeria, popularly known as a 'palace coup', headed by General Ibrahim Babangida. Babangida, the so-called 'Maradona' of Nigerian politics, who deceived Nigerians with his unfulfilled promises of handover to a democratically elected government in early 1990s. The transitions were successively postponed, but the end was the unpopular annulment of the June 12, 1993 presidential election judged by expert analysts as the most credible election ever to have been held in Nigeria (Banjo, 2010).

Largely because of international and national pressure on the military junta, General Babangida stepped aside and installed a weak administration popularly known as the Interim National Government headed by Chief Ernest Shonekan, who was sworn in as Nigeria's ninth head of state. The move was to the amazement of Nigeria and the world as the choice was not the self-proclaimed winner of the June 12 presidential election, Chief M. K. Abiola. The ING was generally viewed as lacking a popular mandate, it were not surprise that the ING had lasted for barely three months when on 17 November 1993 the then Head of State claimed to have resigned. In fact it was yet another coup d'état in Nigeria (Banjo, 2010). The only thing that looked different from the previous coups was the mild nature of the military takeover; but that could be attributed to the weakness of the ING. The government was largely regarded as illegitimate in view of the circumstances that had brought it to power.

The leader of the new military regime in Nigeria was General Sani Abacha, who announced the suspension of all democratic structures and activities as usual with military leadership but to public dismay, constitutional provisions were quickly replaced by arbitrary decrees, which paved the way for the junta to embark on gross human rights abuses in disregard of the judiciary. The regime soon faced unprecedented opposition from human rights groups and crusaders for democracy because Abacha was seen by many as an insider of the Babangida's military junta, who could only extend Babangida's agenda in the Aso-rock (Abuja), Nigeria's sit of power. Ababach's response in the face of opposition was use of brutal force through the State security apparatus. Banjo (2010) summed it up when he wrote that the military government was characterized by extrajudicial killings, assassinations, and torture by the state

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security, the abrogation of civil liberties, and the curtailment of political and labour affiliation. Nigeria at this stage entered into one of the worst stages of human rights abuse of its history.

General Sani Abacha's resolve to remain in power instead of democratizing further aggravated the poor human rights situation in the country as he went on to arrest and detain, Chief M. K. Abiola who was widely known as the winner of the June 12, 1993 presidential election. President Nelson Mandela, who had ascended to a position of international personality, visited Nigeria in 1995 to plead for the release of Abiola (Banjo, 2010). Banjo identified three major sources of pressure on President Mandela: President Clinton's administration in the US, African leaders, and Abiola's family and supporters. The Nigerian government downplayed the Mandela visit as merely a solidarity visit which South African diplomatic sources disputed and blamed Abacha as the man who was plunging Nigeria into political crises assessed to be similar to what had happened in Rwanda (Banjo, 2010).

At this stage Mandela's growing international prestige brought more pressure on him from Western and African leaders in both non-governmental and governmental institutions to step up initiatives that would resolve the Nigerian crisis and secure the release of Abiola. Mandela took a further step by sending the renowned South African Nobel Peace Prize laureate, Archbishop Desmond Tutu, to Abuja in April 1995. The move still did not yield any result as Abacha did not promise anything, and Tutu reported back to Mandela that his attempt was fruitless. However, he advised that Mandela should consult further with Abacha (Banjo, 2010).

In another poor move of the military junta, a group of purported coup plotters who were suspected of plotting to overthrow the Abacha regime were arrested, the most prominent of whom were General Olusegun Obasanjo (former Nigerian head of state), and Major-General Shehu Musa Yar' Adua. Mandela yet again made significant effort to intervene by sending his deputy president, Thabo Mbeki to Nigeria in July 1995. The move was a calculated attempt by Mandela to capitalize on the diplomatic experience of his able deputy who had negotiated so much for the ANC during the apartheid struggle. He had also been the ANC's representative in Nigeria between 1976 and 1978 at a time Obasanjo was Nigeria's military head of state. Mbeki's three-day working visit did not bear fruit because Abacha made no promise to release Abiola and other important political detainees (Banjo, 2010).

During the Commonwealth summit in Auckland, Mandela's conviction that he had received General Sani Abacha's firm promise of clemency for the 'Ogoni nine' (Ken Sarowiwa and eight others) was to no effect when he learnt of their sudden execution. Mandela felt betrayed because of his assurance to fellow Commonwealth leaders that the executions would not take effect. He believed he had used his moral stature to discourage Abacha from carrying out the hangings, and angrily accused Abacha of behaving like a frightened dictator who engaged in extra-judicial killings (Banjo, 2010). He concurred with the British premier, John Major that Abacha was sitting on a volcano and he promised to explode it under him. He called on the West to impose oil sanctions on Abacha's regime, and advocated Nigeria's expulsion from the Commonwealth (Adebajo, 2007). This simply meant a switch of position between Nigeria and South Africa. In the apartheid days, Nigeria had successfully championed the expulsion of South Africa from the Commonwealth, which was successful and held until the end of apartheid (Arema, 2013).

On his return home, Mandela recalled his High Commissioner to Nigeria, George Nene, who had been somewhat heavily criticized by South African civil society groups for failing to make contact with Nigerian opposition groups, and being close to unscrupulous leaders in Abuja. Nigerian leaders felt otherwise – that Nene had become too close to the opposition, and had lost all understanding with the Abacha led government in Abuja (Adebajo, 2007).

2.1 Nigeria Withdraws from 1996 African Cup of Nations

In December 1995, Mandela called on SADC summit to take collective action against Nigeria on the grounds of human rights abuse and indiscriminate extrajudicial killing. According to Banjo and Omidiran, (2000), Abacha responded by refusing to let the Nigerian Super Eagles defend their African Cup of Nations gold medal (which the Nigerian team had won in 1994 in Tunis) in South Africa in 1996. In Nigeria's calculation, the first indication that South Africa intended to use sports as a weapon was when South Africa withdrew the invitation of Nigeria's Super Eagles to the four-nation tournament organized by South Africa. The South African Football Association alleged that it was because of the hanging of the 'Ogoni 9' that the invitation was withdrawn. The Nigerian sports authorities protested to FIFA asking for South Africa to be punished for mixing sport with politics. Nigeria based her argument on the ground that suspension of Nigeria from the Commonwealth because of the killing of the 'Ogoni 9' was a political issue which should not have influenced sports decisions. FIFA agreed but only warned South Africa, promising, however, to punish her if there were any future occurrence of mixture of sport and politics (Banjo and Omidiran, 2000).

Nigeria, a master specialist in using sport to advance political interest, recalled that CAF 1996 in South Africa provided an ample opportunity for her to outsmart South Africa in this time of diplomatic breakdown between the two countries. This would be similar to the positions that Nigeria had taken on sport to score political points against the apartheid regime. Chief Tom Ikimi, Nigeria's Foreign Affairs Minister who was also the former Chairman of the defunct.

National Republican Convention (NRC), one of the political parties that contested elections in Nigeria's failed third republic, wanted success in defending the worst Nigerian notorious regime around the world (Banjo and Omidiran, 2000). He was said to have presented a shabby and highly contested report of the hostile attitude South Africa promised Nigeria's team, sports officials and supporters if they dared come to South Africa in 1996. The main thrust of the report which was obtained from Nigeria's High Commission in South Africa was that there would be no Nigerian representatives in the competition (Banjo and Omidiran, 2000). The South African decision to deny Nigeria's then Minister of Sport, Chief Jim Nwaobodo a visa constituted evidence, though under CAF and FIFA rules South Africa was not obliged to issue visas to officials of a sports ministry but only to players, fans, and officials of Football Associations (Banjo and Omidiran, 2000). However, refusal of visa application to such a high profile Nigerian was not acceptable to the leadership.

The situation was further aggravated by Nigeria's Minister of Information, Walter Ofonagoro's, accusation of Nelson Mandela of being a black head of a white country' who could not be trusted. Adebajo (2007) observed that it was a particularly hurtful and insensitive statement that hit at the most sensitive spot of a black-led government that had inherited a country in which whites still controlled the economy and economic institutions. Continuing, he explained that ordinarily South Africans would not easily forgive Nigeria for this personal slur on the country's saintly hero. Mandela's inexperience in the complexities of African diplomacy was shown in his inability, despite his iconic status, to acquire a single Southern African state to take action against Nigeria.

In the end, Nigeria boycotted the 1996 CAF competition in South Africa (Banjo, 2010). This was clearly a situation that could have been managed better if not for the misuse of words on the part of South Africa who was so much dependent upon the personality and moral status of its President. Nigeria on its part was pretending that all was well with its internal politics and the military leaders in Nigeria miscalculated by expressing that Nigeria's relations with South Africa should only be defined by its contribution to the peaceful end of apartheid. Both countries undermined real issues in foreign policy

2.2 The Revival of Relations Between Nigeria and South Africa

In June 1998 General Sani Abacha's untimely death seemed to have turned events around between the two countries. The South African Deputy President, Thabo Mbeki, travelled to Nigeria to urge the newly appointed head of state, General Abdulsalami Abubakar, to release political prisoners, protect human rights, and ensure press freedom and turn on the green light for safe return of exiles (Banjo, 2010). In August the same year, General Abdulsalami Abubakar returned the visit. Abubakar also extended an invitation to President Nelson Mandela to the ECOWAS summit to be hosted in Abuja, Nigeria. These moves paved the way for the revival of cooperation between the two countries (Banjo, 2010). The gentle Abubakar handed over to a democratically elected government on 29 May 1999, imitating President de Klerk who had earlier in 1994 piloted the transition from apartheid to democracy in South Africa. Interestingly, General Olusegun Obasanjo, who succeeded General Abubakar, would on his first foreign trip as democratically elected President of Nigeria attend the inauguration of his friend, Thabo Mbeki, as President of South Africa in June of the same year.

Not long after, improvement of relations between the two countries was to depend largely on the Binational Commission which was a strategic coordination of economic bilateralism between the two countries. The commission was formally established in October 1999, to be co-chaired by the Vice-President and Deputy President of Nigeria and South Africa respectively (Banjo, 2010). According to Adebajo, (2007), the Binational Commission has major objectives which he highlighted as being to provide a framework for joint efforts to bring Africa into the mainstream of global political, social, and economic developments; provide the basis for the government and private sectors of both countries to consult with each other to promote bilateral trade and industry; improve bilateral relations in the fields of technology, education, health, culture, youth, and sports; use both countries' human and natural resources to maximize socio-economic development through collaborative efforts; and establish the mechanisms to promote peace, stability, and socio-economic integration in Africa. According to Adebajo, (2007), Nigeria and South Africa held six BNC meetings, alternating them between the two countries. Those meetings were held in October 1999, April 2000, March 2001, March 2002, December 2003 and September 2004.

According to Adebajo, (2007), the BNC intended to address some issues that have negatively affected the relationship between Tshwane and Abuja including Nigerian diplomats complaining about negative South African press reports and xenophobic stereotypes depicting Nigerians as drug traffickers and criminals. Nigerian diplomats contend that local South Africans, Chinese, Asians, Europeans and Arabs are also engaged in the illegal business of drug dealing, but they are not tarred with it. A Johannesburg radio station, 94.7 Highveld, was forced by South Africa's Broadcasting Complaints Commission to apologize after it claimed that the Nigerian President, Olusegun Obasanjo, was carrying cocaine in his bag when he came to attend Mbeki's inauguration in June 2004 (Adebajo, 2007). In spite of the framework of BNC and numerous bilateral agreements Nigeria has signed with South Africa, the two countries have not been able to maintain absolute cordial diplomatic relation. There have also been minor sporadic diplomatic breakdowns between the two countries, but another worrisome crisis broke out in 2012 popularly known as yellow fever card deportation.

2.3 Nigeria-South Africa Bilateral Relations

It is evident that since independence in 1960, Africa has remained at the forefront of Nigeria's foreign policy. This nucleus of her foreign policy saw the country committing herself fanatically to decolonization of the African continent and eradication of racial discrimination and domination. According to Onouha (2008) "the first opportunity for Nigeria to implement her foreign policy on anticolonialism was provided by the Shapeville massacre of 21st March 1960. During the incident, the white South African police attacked South African blacks protesting against racial discrimination and

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domination." This incident which led to the death of 72 blacks with many wounded "marked the beginning of Nigeria's diplomatic confrontations with South Africa." This incidence and other ugly racial incidences in South Africa saw Nigeria spearheading the call for political and economic sanctions against the apartheid South Africa in the International Community. Examples were the suspension of South Africa from the Commonwealth in 1961 and the imposition of trade embargo under the auspices of the Organization of African Unity (O.A.U). Nigeria was instrumental to the call for complete isolation of South Africa by the International Community.

As a result of the pressure mounted by Nigeria and other nations of the world, Non-government Organizations and influential individuals, the racist regime of South Africa collapsed in 1991. "With the obituary of apartheid in 1991, the need for change in diplomatic strategies arose." (Onuoha op. cit). The degree of the solidarity, support and sacrifice which the government and people of Nigeria exhibited in the quest for the elimination of apartheid and the enthronement of democracy and majority rule in South Africa was such that Nigeria, not minding the geographical distance, became identified as a frontline state.

At the dawn of democracy in South Africa, Nigerians, especially the professionals, were part of those that started to migrate to South Africa. Part of the philosophy of those early migrants was to contribute to the much needed nation building in post apartheid South Africa.

With a democratic and majority rule in place in South Africa in 1994, South Africa quickly switched over the Pariah Status in the International Community with Nigeria. The military government in Nigeria with its human rights abuses attracted the wrath of the International Community. South Africa now became the "aggressor" as it used its position as emerging African Superpower to campaign for the suspension of Nigeria from the Commonwealth and the United Nations.

"Nigeria - South Africa confrontations reached its zenith in 1995 when the then South African President, Nelson Mandela vigorously campaigned for the expulsion of Nigeria from Commonwealth during the Commonwealth Summit in Auckland."

With democratic government in place in Nigeria in 1999, Nigeria - South Africa relations became less confrontational but friendly and cordial. Prior to 1999 South Africa had a poor political relationship with Nigeria. At the time, Nigeria was ruled by a military junta that was politically hostile to South Africa. This, however dramatically changed with the end of the military government and the return of democracy in 1999. From that point on, the South African State built a strong relationship with the Nigerian government under the leadership of Obasanjo and Yar'Adua. This relationship was also helped by the fact that Thabo Mbeki had formed a strong friendship with Obasanjo and Yar'Adua when he was in exile in Nigeria from 1976 to 1979 (Dubow 2000).

Nigeria and South Africa are the emerging giants of Africa. Politically, both countries are the dominant state entities in their respective sub-regions. They also have a history of cooperation with, and involvement in, a range of continental projects like the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD).

The two countries have always added their voices in appreciating the new commitment to African development programmes by the developed world, and ensure that engagement with the developed world meets Africa's objective of extricating the continent from underdevelopment. They have also worked closely on conflict prevention and resolution, the establishment and operationalisation of the African Union, and put forward a detailed blueprint for sustainable development for Africa.

2.3.1 Bilateral Political Relations

Bilateral political relations between South Africa and Nigeria are strong with Nigeria considered as one of South Africa's important partners on the African continent in advancing the vision of Africa's political and economic renewal.

The leaders of both countries have traversed the globe spreading the idea of African renaissance - focusing largely on democracy, development and security and seeking foreign investments to revive Africa's ailing economies. They have called for greater international burden-sharing in peacekeeping missions, campaigns for the annulment of Africa's external debt, championed better access for African goods entering western markets and called for Africa's integration into the global economy in fairer terms.

It will be recalled that the former Heads of State of Nigeria and South Africa, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo and Thabo Mbeki worked relentlessly to lobby the rich nations of the world to focus greater attention on African problems. At the G8 meeting of the world's richest states in 2000, both leaders argued strongly that the rich nations should forgive Africa's debt. Both had called for technology and resource transfer from the West to Africa, criticizing the gap between promise and delivery on the part of most Western states. NEPAD, championed by Mbeki and Obasanjo proposed a simple bargain: the West provides debt relief, opens its markets, invests in Africa and supports peacekeeping missions in exchange for democratic accountability and financial probity by African leaders through a self-monitored peer review mechanism. Both leaders have common aspirations for a united and prosperous democratic Africa. Thabo Mbeki's dream to play a leading role in Africa's socio-economic development merged with Obasanjo's dream of economic diplomacy which led to series of consultations and meetings by the leaders of both countries.

The meetings of both countries since the past decade underscore the need for greater coordination of regional mechanisms for conflict prevention, management and resolution within the African Union mechanism and the United Nations Security Council.

Both countries have continuously stressed the imperative of ensuring that peace and stability becomes a reality in Africa. In one of their meetings in Abuja, the Heads of State Summit emphasized a need for an effective peer review mechanism, which would be designed, owned and managed by Africans. This mechanism, the Heads of State emphasized, must be credible, transparent and all-encompassing, to demonstrate that African leaders are fully aware of their responsibilities and obligations to their peoples. It is noteworthy to emphasize that the institution of Peer Review mechanism was championed by Nigeria and South Africa.

2.3.2 Nepad: Nigeria-South Africa Initiative

New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) is an African led strategy for economic development and poverty eradication from the African continent. NEPAD recognizes Africa's responsibility to create the conditions for development by ending conflict, improving economic and political governance and strengthening regional integration. It is based on the principles of good governance as basic requirement for peace, security and sustainable political and socio-economic development. It is also based on African ownership and full utilization of African resources for development. Nigeria and South Africa undoubtedly played an indispensable role in the establishment of NEPAD.

Without the leadership of Nigeria and South Africa, the creation of NEPAD would have been more difficult, if not impossible. The creation of NEPAD was predicated on the believe by South African and Nigerian leaders that the regional document will reposition Africa on the path of long term development and reduce her marginalization in international economic relations (Adams, 2006).

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The thinking among the leaders of those two countries and other founding members of this initiative is that "if the continent is to matter in the international community in the decades of 2000's and beyond, there is need to rethink the development strategy" (Omoweh 2003). While the long term objectives of NEPAD include (a) eradicating poverty in Africa and to place African countries on the path of sustainable growth and development and thus halt the marginalization of African globalization process and (b) to promote the role of women in all activities; the short and medium term objectives include among others:

- Strengthening the mechanisms for conflict prevention, management and resolution at the sub-regional and continental levels and to ensure that these mechanisms are used to restore and maintain peace.
- Promoting and protecting democracy and human rights in their respective countries and regions by developing clear standards of accountability, transparency and participatory governance at the national and sub-national levels.
- Building the capacity of the states in Africa to set and enforce the legal framework and maintain law and order (Adams, op cit).

Nigeria and South Africa see NEPAD as opening a new and different chapter in Africa's development. Their thinking corroborates Brian Posthumus' view which presents NEPAD as "the hope for turning back the clock of delay in Africa" (Posthumus, 2009). Nigeria and South Africa agree jointly that NEPAD represents a tacit recognition of the existence of developmental crisis and believe that there is a need to tackle it through this continental initiative.

Both countries believe that NEPAD has become the defining process in the quest for long term development.

This is a reminder to Adams (2006) assertion that "the opportunities and benefits of the regional initiative for African nations, individually and collectively, have been stressed by African leaders and their western allies, especially members of the G.8 group, who have pledged their support."

African leaders with Nigeria and South Africa at the forefront realized that if Africa is to matter in the international community in the 21st century, there is the need for it to rethink its development strategy (Omoweh, 2003). Hence the establishment of New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) under the leadership of both countries. It is believed by both countries and other African leaders that NEPAD will reposition the African continent on the path of long term development and minimize her marginalization and neglect in international economic relations. NEPAD is therefore a commitment by African leaders to accelerate the integration of the African continent into the global economy, as well as a call to the rest of the world to partner with Africa in her own development on the basis of her own agenda and programme of action (Ebegbulem et al., 2012).

NEPAD is based on the principles of good governance as basic requirement for peace, security and sustainable political and socioeconomic development. It is based on African ownership and full utilization of African resources for development. It rested on African ownership and leadership and participation of all sectors of African society.

2.3.3 Bilateral Economic Relations

Since the inception of democratic rule in Nigeria, South Africa and Nigeria have had encouraging bilateral economic relations. Since then, South Africa has emerged among the top investors in many sectors of the Nigerian economy.

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South African companies' presence is visible in the Nigerian economy, especially in areas such as telecommunication, engineering, banking, retail, hospitality, property development, construction and tourism, to mention a few. In terms of technology and infrastructure, South Africa has an edge over Nigeria while Nigeria has an advantage of large market potentials for investments over South Africa. This is why there are a lot of South African companies with huge investments in Nigeria.

In 1999, the South African and Nigerian governments signed bilateral agreements on trade and investment. These agreements amongst other things, aimed to increase the amount of trade and investment between South Africa and Nigeria (Sifingo 2003). The signing of these agreements witnessed inter-alia (a) improved trade relations between South Africa and Nigeria and (b) South African corporations as big players in the Nigerian economy. On improved trade relations between both countries, we saw that the volume of trade between South Africa and Nigeria increased from 1999. Prior to 1999, trade between the two countries was minimal. In 1994, South Africa exported US\$8.1 million worth of products to Nigeria; while it imported US\$3.1 million worth of commodities from that country (Omojola 2006).

With the signing of the South Africa - Nigeria bilateral trade agreement, the situation changed. "By 2005 South Africa was exporting goods to the value of R3.4 billion to Nigeria and importing R4.2 billion worth of commodities from Nigeria (Tenikin 2007). South Africa's exports to Nigeria include machinery, electrical equipment, appliances, wood, paper, prepared food stuffs, beverages, plastics, rubber, chemicals etc. However, oil makes up 97% of Nigeria's exports to South Africa (Pahad 2002). The situation means that South Africa is exporting a wide range of goods to Nigeria, many of which are value added manufactured goods.

As a result of this, South Africa's exports have the potential to grow dramatically. Conversely, Nigeria's export products to South Africa consist of a single raw material in the form of oil. Its oil exports to South Africa are unlikely to increase dramatically over the next few years and its export products are also unlikely to diversify. This translates into an unequal trade situation between South Africa and Nigeria; in which South Africa is in fact the dominant partner in terms of trade relations. What really highlights the unequal relationship that exists between Nigeria and South Africa, however, is the fact that South African companies have come to dominate many sectors of the Nigerian economy, with no known holistic succor from Nigeria government to her indigenous companies.

2.3.4 South African Companies as Big Players in the Nigerian Economy

Prior to 1999, there were only 4 South African companies operating in Nigeria (Ezeoha and Uche 2005). This situation has dramatically changed with the assistance of the South African State, and the signing of bilateral agreements and the establishment of South Africa - Nigeria Bi-national Commission. Today, there are over 100 South African companies doing business in Nigeria (Sifinan, 2003). Within a mere 8 years, South African companies have become major players in almost every sector of the Nigerian economy.

The biggest investment by South African companies in Nigeria has been in the telecommunication sector. In 2001, MTN was awarded a license by the Nigerian government to operate a cell phone network in the country. In return, MTN had to pay licensing fees of over US\$285 million. Added to this, MTN has spent a further US\$1billion on setting up its operations in Nigeria (Lutchman et al., 2004). Currently, MTN is the largest cellular network company in Nigeria with over 10million subscribers (Tenekin, 2007).

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South African companies have also become dominant players in Nigeria's construction sector. Entech, a South African based engineering company, headed a consortium of South African companies that were awarded a tender worth R2.1billion from the Lagos State government to redevelop the Bar Beach and Victoria Island area of Lagos (Pahad, 2002) Many large South African companies have also invaded the tourism and leisure sector in Nigeria. Under NEPAD, the South African parastatal, the Industrial Development Corporation (IDC) has become one of the largest investors in Nigeria's tourist sector.

To date it has invested over US\$1.4 billion in tourism and telecommunications ventures in Nigeria (United Nations Report, 2005). Another major player in the tourism sector is the South African Company, Bidvest. Through its subsidiary, Tom-vest, it has purchased one of the biggest tourism companies in Nigeria, Touchdown Travels. The biggest development in the Nigerian tourism sector however, is the massive Tinapa project in the Cross-River state. This project falls under the auspices of NEPAD and has the full backing of the South African and Nigerian governments. South African companies are also heavily involved in Nigeria's media and entertainment sector. DSTV, as a major force in the television industry, accounts for 90% of the viewers that watch satellite TV in Nigeria between 2005 and 2009. This has seen DSTV growing into the sixth largest company listed on the Lagos Stock Exchange. (Omojola, 2006).

According to Jonah Onuoha, "as at mid-April 2003, an estimated 55 South African companies were doing business in Nigeria. The single largest investor is MTN". Its entrance into the Nigerian market came by way of the first telecommunications auctions process in Africa, in January 2001. At that time MTN's entrance into the Nigerian market was the company's single biggest investment outside South Africa (Onuoha, 2008).

The need for improved bilateral economic relations between the two countries gave birth to South Africa - Nigeria Bi-national Commission.

2.3.5 The South Africa - Nigeria Bi-National Commission

In October 1999, a South Africa-Nigeria Bi-national Commission (BNC) was established by the South African and Nigerian governments. The Bi-national Commission was established to consolidate and strengthen bilateral political, economic and trade relations between Nigeria and South Africa. It has a mandate to review cooperation between the two countries on foreign affairs, public enterprises and infrastructure, agriculture, minerals and energy, trade, industry and finance among others. The Bi-National Commission has been meeting twice a year ever since and aims to increase the amount of trade and investment between South Africa and Nigeria. The Deputy Presidents of both countries head the commission. At the meetings, trade and investment opportunities in Nigeria and South Africa are identified and plans are put in place so that they can be realized. In this way, many deals that have proved lucrative for South African and Nigerian companies and parastatals have been facilitated through the Bi-national Commission. The broad objectives of the South Africa-Nigeria Bi-National Commission are;

- To provide a framework for collaborative and cooperative efforts in the common endeavour to bring Africa into the mainstream of global political, social and economic developments.
- To provide the basis for the governments and private sectors of both countries to consult each other on their respective economies and investment climates with a view to promoting trade and industry.
- To improve bilateral relations between the two countries in the field of technology, education, health, culture, youth and sports.

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- To utilize the generous endowments of both countries in human and natural resources to maximize socio-economic development, through economies of scale, global competitiveness and specialization based on comparative advantage.
- To establish the mechanisms for putting the benefits of economic cooperation to the service of peace, stability, social integration and economic development in other parts of the continent.

The cooperation of both countries through the South Africa–Nigeria Bi-national Commission seeks to create a climate conducive for the creation of a better quality of life for all. The commission is also seen as a platform in which both countries can jointly as partners impact positively, in conjunction with other African countries, on regional peace and security; socioeconomic development; poverty alleviation; and the prevention of crime and corruption.

Nigeria and South Africa have in recent times sought to advance their mutual interests by intensifying their bilateral relationship through cooperation in the areas of trade, investment, infrastructure development, science and technology, agriculture, minerals and energy, transport and communication et.c. Both countries have been on regular consultations to find ways of establishing common positions on efforts to bring the continent into the mainstream of global economic development.

The Commission has facilitated cooperation between the two countries in areas such as defence and security, science and technology, education and culture. The benefit of this commission to both countries can be seen from the fact that between 1999 and 2002, there was approximately a 540 percent increase in the volume of South Africa’s export to Nigeria (Onuoha, 2008).

As Lutchman and Daniel (2004) noted, in 2003, two-way trade flows between South African and Nigeria amounted to R5.3billion. Further evidence has shown that out of that amount, South Africa’s exports were valued at R2.3billion, while its imports share 98%, of which oil amount to R2.7billion. According to Onuoha (2008), as at mid-April 2003, an estimated 55 South African companies were doing business in Nigeria.

The South Africa-Nigeria Chamber of Commerce arose out of the Bi-national Commission. Some of the largest South African companies that have investments in Nigeria are members of the chamber, such as MTN, Standard Bank, First Rand Massmart, Sun International etc (www.sa.ncc.co.za) The main goal of the South African - Nigerian Chamber of Commerce is to identify investment opportunities in Nigeria for South African Corporations. It also provides information on Nigerian government policies and how to do business in Nigeria. The Chamber of Commerce also conducts market research for South African companies wanting to do business in Nigeria.

The South Africa - Nigeria Binational Commission has been valuable in furthering South Africa's business interest in Nigeria. Indeed, the South African state has used its diplomatic power and the relationship that it has with the Nigerian government to assist South African corporations and parastatals to become big players in the Nigerian economy. Along with this, South Africa, through NEPAD and the signing of the bilateral agreement on trade, has found in Nigeria a very lucrative market for its exports.

The Commission looks at tariffs, work with Standard Organisation of both countries to ensure high standards of export and imports between the two countries.

Jacob Zuma, a former Vice President of South Africa under Thabo Mbeki, observed in 1999 when he visited Nigeria that “inasmuch as many will agree that such bilateral arrangements will be an unequal one because Nigeria is predominantly a consuming nation, Nigeria still exports not just communities but also human resources.” As such, the relationship between the two countries should not be underemphasized. Seeing Nigeria as a consuming nation, South Africa offers a good market to any viable business in Nigeria.

2.4 Yellow Fever Card Deportation

Another major diplomatic row erupted between Nigeria and South Africa, with the former alleging that President Jacob Zuma's led government was 'taking decisions that were disrespectful to Africa. This was as a result of the deportation of 125 Nigerians who landed at OR Tambo International Airport. On 5 March, 2012 the group was prevented from entering South Africa because they did not have the required documentation for vaccination against yellow fever as required by South African port health authorities. Reports showed that 75 of them were sent back home via South African Airways, and another 50 were flown back by the Nigerian airline, Arik Air (Moeng, 2012).

The Soweto reported that Nigeria's Foreign Affairs Minister, Gbenga Ashiru, vowed to reciprocate the gesture by demonstrating that South Africa does not have a monopoly in deporting travelers. In a surprise move, described by many as retaliatory, 28 South Africans were turned back at Murtala Muhammed International Airport in Lagos, and another 56 were deported between 6th and 7th of March 2012.

According to Prof. Bola Akinterinwa the then Director General, Nigerian Institute of International Affairs (NIIA) it would be highly disadvantageous for South Africa to misconstrue Nigeria's tolerance of certain diplomatic excesses as cowardice of diplomatic stand-off, a total of 256 nationals of both powerhouses, Nigeria and South Africa, were carelessly deported to their respective countries without due process. Nigeria this time took a pound of South Africa's flesh by deporting a total of 131 South Africans (Moeng, 2012). According to The Sowetan, the South African International Relations and Cooperation Department's spokesman, Clayson Monyela, claimed that Nigeria was blowing things out of proportion and mixing issues. The Department further stated that it was a health matter, claiming that it was only being elevated to a diplomatic issue by Nigeria (Moeng, 2012).

According to The Sowetan, the South African Department of Home Affairs's spokesperson, Ronnie Mamoepa, also claimed that the Department followed standard international protocol in the deportation. He advised the public to understand that communicable diseases must be controlled. The spokesperson of the Department of health, Fidel Hadebe, was of the opinion that South Africa was in line with the country's policies, which are also in line with WHO (World Health Organization) guidelines on disease control.

However, a gentleman's agreement was reached after the South African government formally sent a letter of apology to Nigeria's Minister of Foreign Affairs, Olugbenga Ashiru, apologizing for barring 125 Nigerians from entry into South Africa over alleged possession of fake yellow fever vaccine cards. Nigeria in turn accepted the apology of the supposedly guilty opponent, South Africa. According to The Sowetan, both countries decided to put in place certain mechanisms to ensure that a similar development does not reoccur. The intention was to protect the bilateral relations and agreements between the two countries. The five measures Nigeria and South Africa agreed upon included:

- The revival of the Bi-national Commission between South Africa and Nigeria and the Immigration Working Group as soon as possible.
- South Africa's national Department of Health and the Gauteng Health Department to reconsider reopening the vaccination clinic at the OR Tambo International Airport so that passengers without the yellow fever card can be vaccinated upon arrival at the airport to avoid undue deportation.
- The South African and Nigerian health authorities would exchange vaccine batch numbers and details about the official institutions that administer the vaccine for verification purposes at the port of entry. This information would also be made available to the missions in Lagos and Abuja

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who issue visas based on the proof of a yellow fever certificate. The airlines will also be informed about the verification process.

- Immigration officials would be the first officials that deal with the travelers at the port of entry, and if they should experience challenges, they should invite other units such as Health to help, and not the other way round.
- In the case of mass deportations, senior officials at the Department of International Relations and Cooperation, including Protocol, should be consulted by Immigration and Health officials at the airport before undertaking such action. This will provide opportunity to senior officials to consult with the Department before deportation of large numbers of people.

3 The African Giants

- a.** The Principle of Non-Alignment: This is a rejection of alliance with the existing ideological and military power blocs of the capitalist West led by the United States and the communist East led by the former Soviet Union during the cold war era. It was particularly important because Nigeria gained independence during the heat of cold war.
- b.** Legal Equality of States: Nigeria adopted the principle of respect for the legal equality, sovereignty and territorial integrity of all states, big or small. This was designed to protect the small and newly independent states from the domineering influence of the developed nations.
- c.** Non Interference in the Domestic Affairs of other state: Nigeria upheld the principle of non-interference in the internal affairs of other countries.
- d.** The Principle of Multilateralism: This implies the freedom to seek membership of both continental and global multilateral organizations.
- e.** Africa as the Centre piece of Nigeria's Foreign Policy: Africa has remained the cornerstone of Nigeria's foreign policy since independence.

It is generally accepted that a vibrant foreign policy derives its strength from domestic imperatives, that is, from the needs of the country and the populace. Africa has remained the centre piece of Nigeria's foreign policy since independence in 1960 (Ajaebili, 2011). The country has therefore spent heavily in pursuit of the decolonization of Africa and terminating the apartheid regime in Pretoria, aggressively championing the freedom of Africans in various countries such as Congo, Angola and Mozambique when they were under the yoke of colonialism, and of others under the minority racist regimes in Zimbabwe and South Africa (Ajaebili, 2011).

Nigeria has played an unmatched role in restoring peace to conflict-ridden African countries such as Congo, Sudan, Liberia and Sierra Leone (Ajaebili, 2011), to which she always committed huge human and material resources. Nigeria has, however, continued to endure the mockery of several African states notwithstanding her big brother role in Africa. For instance, some neighboring Francophone countries embarrass Nigeria and show outright hostility by subjecting Nigerians living in their midst to various forms of torture and other humiliation (Ajaebili, 2011). Nigerians in Southern African countries, and particularly in South Africa, face a similar fate generally termed as xenophobia (see Umezurike and Isike, 2012). This poor perception of Nigerians in the international community could be blamed on the unscrupulous political leadership and economic breakdown which the country has experienced for several years owing to the opportunities squandered by the successive military regimes in the country.

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In 1993, South Africa's apartheid hero and ANC leader, Nelson Mandela, published a detailed exposition of the philosophical pillars that support South Africa's foreign policy. According to him they include:

- that issues of human rights are central to South Africa's international relations and extend beyond the political to economic, social and environmental issues.
- That just and lasting solutions to the problems of humankind can only be achieved through the promotion of democracy in the world.
- That considerations of justice and respect for international law should guide the relations between South Africa and other nations in the world.
- That peace is the goal for which South Africa and all nations should strive, and where this fails, internationally agreed but non-violent methods, including effective arms control regimes, must be employed.
- That the concerns and interests of the continent of Africa should be reflected in South Africa's foreign policy.
- That the economic development of South Africa depends on growing regional and international economic cooperation in an interdependent world.

However, the concept of African Renaissance comprises a philosophy which calls on African people and nations to overcome the current challenges confronting the continent. The concept was popularized by former South African President Thabo Mbeki during his term of office as Deputy President and subsequently President. As such, it has been an essential ingredient of the post-apartheid South African intellectual agenda which has continued to shape South Africa's foreign policy towards Africa. In April 1997 Mbeki articulated the elements that comprise the African Renaissance to include, among other things, social cohesion, democracy, economic rebuilding and growth, and the establishment of Africa as a significant player in the geopolitical affairs of the world. Among other numerous objectives, the African Renaissance is a philosophical and political movement which intends to eradicate the violence, elitism, corruption, poverty and general underdevelopment that has engulfed the African continent, and ultimately replace them with a more just and equitable order. Mbeki proposes doing this by, among other things, encouraging education and the reversal of the brain drain of African intellectuals. He also urges Africans (led by African intellectuals) to take pride in their heritage, and to take charge of their lives. Some scholars have argued that the African Renaissance is equivalent to the Pan-Africanism project which seeks to unite Africa (see Zeleza, 2009).

However, the big question here is: how does South Africa fare in terms of moving from theory to practice of implementing the spirit and vision of the African Renaissance in terms of her foreign policy in Africa? Since the advent of democracy in South Africa in 1994, which marked the end of South Africa's isolation from the rest of the world, she has established her presence and influence in a number of ways, especially in Africa. The notable spheres in which South Africa has played major roles in Africa include sport, economics and political leadership. In sport, South Africa emerged from isolation in 1994 to host the first ever FIFA-organized World Cup on African soil (see Ndlovu, 2010). In economics South Africa has demonstrated that it has the most sophisticated capitalist economy in Africa in terms of trade, debt and foreign investments in Africa and beyond (Mahao, 2006; Tjemolane, 2011; Alden and Soko, 2005; Nicole, 2004). In terms of political leadership, South Africa has emerged as a regional and continental power in peacekeeping and negotiation in conflict areas such as the DRC, Burundi, Angola, Lesotho,

Sudan and Zimbabwe (see Spence, 2004; Habib & Selinyane, 2004; Wannenburg, 2004; Ngubentombi, 2004). But to what extent do all this promote cooperation between Nigeria and South Africa?

3.1 Big Brother Nigeria and Neo-Imperialist South Africa

According to Campbell (2006), Nigeria staged the second World Black and African Festival of Arts and Culture (FESTAC) in 1977. Campbell used the festival to examine the many problems standing in the way of Nigeria's move toward new leadership in the present century. According to him, FESTAC, in fact, revealed a society drifting in the wrong direction. The organizers claimed that the festival was an arena for bringing together peoples of African descent to exhibit and celebrate their shared heritage. Another claim was that it was aimed at exploiting Nigeria's newly attained economic strength and muscle for political advantage on the global scene. But all hopes were soon dashed away because of ethnic and regional division and corruption in the country. According to Campbell, FESTAC was an avenue for looting money. It amounted to big waste in a society in urgent need of economic reform and political revival. It was also a story of grand betrayal and exploitation of the weak, the vulnerable, and the defenseless, orchestrated in large measure in collusion with Western industrial capital Campbell (2006). Such big brother roles as Nigeria had embarked upon, which signified lack of direction in her economic and political leadership, had seen the international respectability of Nigeria diminish remarkably in recent years.

Nigeria was a frontline state in support of liberation movements in Southern Africa because of her commitment to what she considered a just struggle for freedom in the region. For this end Nigeria established the big brother project of the Southern African Relief Fund (SARF) (see Aremu, 2013). This was specially funded with deductions from the salary of every Nigerian worker, irrespective of rank, both in the public and private sectors as well as donations from ordinary Nigerians in all walks of life, including students (see Aremu, 2013). This fund was made available to the liberation movements in Southern Africa. Nigeria further provided scholarships for students from South Africa. Nigerian artists also contributed in this struggle. For instance, Nigerian musicians waxed albums in support of the anti-apartheid struggle. A memorable one in this respect was Sonny Okosun's timeless piece, 'Fire in Soweto'. At the international level, Nigeria provided leadership at the United Nations and the Organization of African Unity (now the African Union). For example, Nigeria chaired the UN Special Committee against Apartheid (UNSCAA) for most of its existence (see Aremu, 2013). Nigeria also championed the isolation of apartheid South Africa until that country's freedom in the 1990s. In sport, Nigeria engineered boycotts and the isolation of South Africa because of apartheid (see Banjo and Omidiran, 2000).

South Africa at freedom in 1994 on the other hand, engaged in an African Renaissance that saw her expand her neo-imperial interests in Africa. For example, South Africa's economic dominance in Africa is demonstrated through her production of approximately 80% of Southern Africa's GDP. A lopsided trade relationship exists between South Africa and her neighbours, with South Africa having a surplus advantage over fellow SADC members. South Africa's estimated economic output is US\$160 billion, far more than that of the other 13 SADC member states, which jointly produce only about US\$33 billion (Alden and Soko, 2005). South Africa has also emerged as the largest foreign investor in Southern Africa. South Africa's direct investment in the 13 SADC countries has been estimated to be over US\$5.4 billion by 2000. According to Alden and Soko, (2005) in 2001, South Africa's investment in Southern Africa is estimated to have amounted to R14.8 billion (US\$20 million) by South African Airways (SAA) for its stake in Air Tanzania; US\$6 billion by Eskom Enterprises in the Inga project in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC); US\$56 million by Sun International in its hotel in Zambia; US\$142 million by Vodacom in Tanzania, and an additional US\$139 million investment in the DRC; US\$53 million by Pretoria Portland Zimbabwe in merger activity in Zimbabwe; a US\$860 million investment by BHP Billiton, the IDC and Mitsubishi in the development of the Mozal aluminium smelter in Mozambique;

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and a further investment of US\$1.1 billion by Sasol in the Pande and Temane gas fields in Mozambique (Alden and Soko, 2005).

South Africa's total trade with the rest of the continent is heavily skewed in her favour. South Africa's exports to Africa, mostly manufactured goods, increased from US\$1.3 billion in 1994 to US\$5.9 billion in 2003, while imports from Africa to South Africa increased from a low base of US\$0.4 billion to US\$1.2 billion during the same period (Alden and Soko, 2005).

South Africa's economic dominance in Africa has seen growth in trade and investment between the two biggest economies in the continent, South Africa and Nigeria, with South Africa taking the lead. Both countries are also Africa's major regional powers in economics and politics. Nigeria has become South Africa's biggest trade partner in West Africa and her third largest on the African continent after Zimbabwe and Mozambique. This compares poorly with a relatively weak balance of trade for Nigeria with South Africa. South Africa's economic foray into Nigeria has been encouraged at the highest political level, even though most firms have entered the country under their own umbrella through the NigeriaSouth Africa Chamber of Commerce. Aremu (2013) reported that South Africa paraded an estimated gross domestic product (GDP) of \$368 billion in 2011 as Africa's biggest economy, while Nigeria, Africa's second biggest economy by GDP, recorded some \$232 billion. Nigeria has regrettably been pushed back to de-industrialization with just less than 4 per cent manufacturing value added to GDP, while South Africa, as the leading industrializing nation in Africa, parades the highest manufacturing value added number of 24 per cent.

In the past decade, over 100 South African companies, with the support of the Department of Trade and Industry, have penetrated the Nigerian market in different economic sectors. Several South African companies now operate in Nigeria. These include: MTN, Eskom Nigeria, South African Airways, Stanbic Merchant Bank Nigeria Ltd., Multichoice Nigeria/M-Net, Umgeni Water, Defresh Products Nigeria Ltd., South Africa-Nigeria Communications and Systems Ltd., Grinaker-LTA Construction Ltd., Protea Hotels, Critical Rescue International, Global Outdoor Semces, Oracle Airtime Sales, and Digital Satellite Television. Only a handful of Nigerian companies have set up business in South Africa. These include Union Bank, First Bank, Philips Consulting, News Media, Financial Standard and This Day Newspapers (Adebajo, 2007; Zeleza, 2009; Aremu, 2013).

4 Conclusion

Nigeria at independence pursued a clear policy of decolonization, and eradication of racism in Africa. She also pursued big brother projects like the sponsorship of liberation movements in Africa and the FASTAC 1977. But evidence shows that largely because of lack of economic and political leadership, the foreign policy of almighty Nigeria became stranded and confused at the time South Africa was freed from apartheid. Nigeria is willing to partner with South Africa on political and economic bases. But Nigeria's leadership is not willing to standby and be embarrassed because of its internal weakness. The weakness is mostly the result of political instability, lack of sound economic direction, and endemic political and economic corruption in the country.

South Africa, on the other hand, at democratization in 1994 felt disappointed that Nigeria, that should have been providing leadership and leading by example in Africa, was still under military rule and experiencing gross human right abuse, all of which South Africa later converted to her advantage. South Africa pursues a foreign policy of a better South Africa, a better Africa and a better world. However, her leaders popularized the African Renaissance which she is using as an umbrella to expand her business treks in the continent. South Africa has the capacity that is required to lead Africa from poverty to prosperity which Nigeria lacks. However, she is able but unwilling to provide the economic leadership similar to the political leadership Nigeria provided during decolonization in Africa and apartheid in South

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Africa. For example, South Africa has allowed xenophobia to damage her human rights standing and international respectability. Unfortunately this highly damaging hostility is directed against African foreigners residing in South Africa.

The diplomatic feuds between Nigeria and South Africa occur largely because of the differences in their attitudes in terms of African need. It could be said that Nigeria is willing to lead Africa in any direction, but cannot do so right now, especially in economics; while South Africa is able but certainly unwilling to make any sort of sacrifice to Africa. Africa is doomed in the 21st century if the continent has to rely on the axis of Nigeria and South Africa. The hegemony of Nigeria and South Africa is not workable at this stage. For both countries to form hegemony for African prosperity, Nigeria needs to be more competitive in the world economy in order to create parity between her and South Africa for peaceful purposes that support the cause of its relations with South Africa. Such parity will accelerate Nigeria's development and like manner open up space for respect from South Africa in its relations with Nigeria.

According to Ayoola (2020), diplomacy cannot be discussed in isolation, internal polity goes a long way to dictate the outcome, the present government though overwhelmed is doing its best for instance in the area of electricity power distribution and issuance of prepaid meters amongst others; however, more still needs to be done with strong political will in resuscitating, developing and building critical national infrastructures, governmental policies that will encourage healthy competition in all state/regions without prejudice or favoritism, bringing about development within the country and making her stand tall among comity of nations. (Osaghae, 1998) The giant at old age: Any hope?

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